

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS OF GENAI DEPLOYMENT IN B2B SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14055380>

Abstract

The article examines the ethical implications of implementing generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) in software development for the B2B sector. The main ethical issues are analyzed, such as the transparency of algorithms, data protection and a decrease in the degree of human control in the automation process. The impact of GenAI on workplaces and the potential risk associated with bias in decisions made using artificial intelligence (AI) are also being studied. The article presents examples of GenAI applications in large companies and discusses recommendations to mitigate risks. Special attention is given to the need for developing ethical standards, improving AI transparency, and ensuring data security for the successful implementation of GenAI in B2B.

Keywords: generative artificial intelligence (GenAI), B2B, software, ethical implications, algorithm transparency, data protection, automation, bias.

Introduction

With the advancement of technology, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an integral part of business processes, especially in the B2B (business-to-business) sector. In recent years, generative AI models (GenAI), which can create content, analyze data, and automate complex processes based on machine learning algorithms, have gained significant popularity. The use of such technologies opens new opportunities for accelerating software development, optimizing business processes, and improving customer interactions through chatbots and virtual assistants.

The primary advantage of integrating GenAI into software development is the significant reduction in

time and costs for performing routine tasks. However, along with these obvious benefits, a range of ethical concerns arises. The goal of this article is to analyze the ethical consequences of using GenAI in B2B.

Main part. Aspects of GenAI application in B2B software development

Technologies using AI are developing rapidly, transforming approaches to software development in the B2B sector. One of the most significant achievements of recent years is the development of GenAI, which is capable of not only analyzing large volumes of data but also creating new software (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Process of GenAI software development [1]

The process of developing software using GenAI involves several stages, beginning with data preprocessing, collection, and model training. Afterward, the model is optimized to improve its performance, and then it is used to generate content, such as program code. The final stage is evaluating the quality and accuracy of the generated solutions to ensure they meet development requirements. The implementation of such technologies allows for the detection of complex patterns in data and their use to produce results that can replace human labor in many areas.

One of the most notable technological advances driving the spread of GenAI is the development of deep

learning and neural networks. Models have demonstrated that algorithms are capable of creating high-quality texts, images, and other types of content that are hard to distinguish from those created by humans. These systems can learn from vast datasets, including millions of texts, images, or audio files, and generate new solutions based on this knowledge. In parallel, computing power has increased, making the training and deployment of deep AI models more accessible to a larger number of companies. Specifically, cloud computing and specialized hardware solutions, such as Graphics Processing Units (GPU) and Tensor Processing Units (TPU), have helped reduce the costs of creating and using GenAI.

The use of GenAI offers businesses significant advantages, transforming software development processes and business operations as a whole (table 1).

Table 1.

Business advantages of using GenAI [2, 3]

Advantage	Description	Usage example
Improving efficiency	Automation of complex and routine processes allows you to reduce task execution time, increasing productivity.	Acceleration of software development using AI code generation.
Cost reduction	Reducing the need for human labor to perform standard tasks reduces operating costs.	Optimization of operating costs in logistics processes through automation.
Acceleration of development processes	Accelerated code generation and automated testing shorten the software development cycle.	Fast generation of MVP (Minimum Viable Product) products and prototypes in IT companies.
Automation of routine tasks	Generative models can perform repetitive tasks such as testing, reporting, and data management.	Automation of large database management in retail.
Improving the quality of software products	Using GenAI helps to avoid errors and improve product quality by automatically finding and correcting errors in the code.	Automatic testing and error correction in complex software systems.
Personalization of services and solutions	The use of AI models allows you to adapt offers, solutions and services to the needs of each client, improving an individual approach.	Providing personalized recommendations in e-commerce.
Optimizing the customer experience	By analyzing customer behavior and interaction data, companies can offer better customer service.	Chatbots and virtual assistants in customer support.
Forecasting and data analysis	Using data to create accurate forecasts and analytics, which helps companies make informed business decisions.	Big data analysis for forecasting demand in production.

Implementation of GenAI significantly accelerates and optimizes software development processes, reduces operational costs, and improves the quality of the products created. It provides companies with new tools for service personalization, enhancing customer interactions, and making informed decisions based on predictions and data analysis. However, for the successful integration of this technology into business processes, it is crucial to plan carefully and adapt solutions to the specific needs of each company and industry.

Many companies have already begun actively adopting GenAI in their work. One of the most prominent examples is **BCG**, which actively uses GenAI in software development for clients in the industrial sector. They helped create a system that automatically generates code for software solutions managing industrial equipment, adapting it to the specific needs of each factory. This allowed the company to more quickly adapt to market changes and speed up the deployment of new production capacities while maintaining high levels of accuracy and operational safety [4].

Another example is **Bain & Company**, which collaborated with one of the largest financial firms in the United States to implement GenAI technologies in software development. This solution helped speed up the risk assessment process, reduce errors in credit scoring, and make decision-making more transparent [5].

The use of GenAI technologies in software development is radically transforming the B2B sector, providing companies with efficient tools to automate processes, reduce costs, and improve product quality.

Main ethical issues of using GenAI in B2B software development

The integration of GenAI into software development for the B2B sector opens up new opportunities for accelerating processes, automating routine tasks, and increasing productivity. However, such technologies also bring significant ethical challenges, which are especially critical when creating and implementing software.

One of the most serious ethical issues in software development using GenAI is **the lack of transparency in algorithms**. Algorithms based on deep neural networks can automatically generate code, tests, and analytics, but they often remain «black boxes» – complex systems whose internal processes and decision-making methods are difficult to interpret. Software developers and users may not fully understand how GenAI generates solutions and code, which raises questions about their quality and reliability.

It is especially important to note that a lack of transparency affects trust between businesses and their clients. If software developers using GenAI cannot explain how a particular piece of code or technical decision was generated, this can cause clients to doubt the reliability and security of the product. An example of this is when automatic recommendations for the security or architecture of an application, generated by AI, contain implicit errors or vulnerabilities that are difficult to detect until the software is in operation. Trust in developed products and GenAI algorithms directly depends on a company's ability to ensure the transparency and interpretability of AI-generated solutions. There-

fore, to address this issue, software developers must actively work on creating methods for explaining algorithmic decisions and conducting audits of generated code.

Developing software using GenAI requires a large amount of data used to train the algorithms. This data can include both client data and a company's technical data. In the B2B sector, this is a particularly sensitive issue, as the data used for training may contain confidential information – from financial reports and strategic plans to personal data of employees and partners. The main ethical challenge is ensuring the **proper protection of such data**. If software developers using GenAI do not ensure high standards of data security and confidentiality, it can lead to data leaks or misuse. For example, if the training dataset contains insufficiently anonymized data, it may violate regulations like GDPR (General data protection regulation), leading to serious legal consequences for the company. It is especially important for software developers to ensure compliance with data protection norms by establishing strict protocols for data anonymization and protection. This also applies to preventing the potential misuse of data after the development process is completed.

The **ethicity of decisions** made by GenAI is particularly important in the software development process. When AI systems automatically generate code, tests, and other elements of software products, there is a risk that the generated solutions may be unethical or biased. For example, automated algorithms may unintentionally introduce biases into programs, which can lead to discrimination or incorrect user evaluation. This issue is especially relevant when using GenAI for making automated decisions that can affect business partners and clients. In B2B software development, the automation of decisions, such as selecting architectural solutions, assessing security, or managing access, can lead to unpredictable consequences [6]. For example, if the system incorrectly assesses potential risks and blocks access to critical functions, it can cause damage to the client's business. The question arises as to who is responsible for such decisions – software developers, companies implementing GenAI, or the users themselves. The responsibility for errors that occur in the process of working with AI-generated software must be clearly defined, and ethical standards for automated decisions must be carefully considered.

The integration of GenAI into software development may lead to a **reduction in human control over processes**. Although automating code development, testing, and other aspects helps speed up processes and reduce costs, there is a risk of losing human control over important stages of software creation. Developers relying on automated tools may overlook important details or allow errors that are difficult to detect without human involvement.

One example is the automatic generation of tests. GenAI can create test suites for software verification; however, if such tests are not thoroughly reviewed by developers, critical errors or vulnerabilities may be missed. This is particularly dangerous in the B2B sector, where errors in software can have serious consequences for the client's business [7].

The reduction of human involvement in software development jeopardizes not only product quality but also jobs. The automation of many tasks using GenAI may reduce the demand for programmers and testers, leading to social and economic consequences. Developers need to find a balance between automation and maintaining human control to prevent these problems.

The ethical issues arising from the use of GenAI in software development for the B2B sector require careful analysis and consideration. The transparency of algorithms, data protection, the ethics of automated solutions and the preservation of human control are the main aspects that must be taken into account when developing and implementing such technologies. To successfully use GenAI in B2B development, companies must create reliable monitoring and regulatory mechanisms to ensure the safety and fairness of processes while minimizing risks for clients and businesses.

Solutions and recommendations for ethical GenAI implementation in b2b software development

The ethical challenges that arise when integrating GenAI into B2B software development require comprehensive solutions aimed at minimizing risks and ensuring process safety. These solutions must consider both the technological and social aspects of GenAI use, so that companies can take advantage of its benefits without harm to clients and partners.

One of the first steps towards the ethical use of GenAI in software development is **raising awareness and educating employees** about the potential risks and ethical issues associated with AI. This includes developing and conducting training programs for all participants in the software development process – from developers to managers and executives. Awareness of ethical risks, such as algorithmic bias, data confidentiality, and the lack of transparency in decisions, will help companies better manage their processes and minimize potential negative consequences [8]. Companies working in the B2B sector should train their specialists on responsible data use, model transparency, and the prevention of discriminatory algorithms. It is important that software developers and project managers are aware of the potential risks of using AI and can apply strategies to mitigate them.

Information campaigns and seminars can help increase the understanding of ethical issues among developers and executives, ensuring a more conscientious approach to software creation. Companies should strive to foster a culture of ethical GenAI use, which includes continuous employee education, discussing ethical challenges, and evaluating the impacts on clients and partners.

Effective and safe use of GenAI in software development is impossible without clearly defined **ethical frameworks and standards**. To achieve this, companies must develop and implement internal codes and guidelines that will regulate the use of generative models during development. These standards should include provisions on algorithm transparency, data protection, AI decision responsibility, and bias prevention.

One way to enhance ethical transparency is to **introduce AI audits**, where independent experts evaluate

the correctness of GenAI operations and their compliance with ethical standards. Companies can also develop **open-source software**, allowing users and clients to verify algorithms and decision-making methods, which will increase trust in the products and reduce the risk of unethical use of technologies.

An important aspect of ethical GenAI integration is **collaboration** between various stakeholders – companies, regulators, and experts in ethics and technology. Joint efforts are necessary to create a safe and responsible ecosystem for GenAI use in the B2B sector. Companies should actively engage with government agencies and expert organizations to develop regulations that govern the use of AI in software development.

Ethical integration of GenAI into B2B software development requires a comprehensive approach, including education, ethical standards development, and active collaboration between companies, regulators, and experts. Raising awareness of risks and ethical challenges, creating clear ethical frameworks and standards, and coordinating the efforts of all participants will help make GenAI use in the B2B sector safe, responsible, and transparent. Ultimately, this will build long-term client trust and ensure stable growth for companies using AI for software development.

Conclusion

The integration of GenAI into B2B software development represents a significant step in the digital transformation of businesses. This powerful tool can significantly boost productivity, speed up development processes, and optimize customer interactions, making it attractive to companies looking to strengthen their market position. However, along with these technological advantages, serious ethical issues arise that cannot be ignored.

Algorithm transparency, data confidentiality, the ethics of automated decisions, and reduced human control – these are all aspects that must be considered when developing and implementing GenAI-based software. Companies' inability to properly address these issues could lead to a loss of client trust, legal consequences, and reputational damage.

To ensure that GenAI is used successfully and sustainably, companies must develop and implement ethical frameworks, raise employee awareness of risks, and

actively collaborate with regulators and experts in ethics. A comprehensive approach, combining technological innovation and ethical responsibility, will not only avoid potential negative consequences but also ensure the long-term growth of businesses in a rapidly evolving digital economy. Therefore, responsible GenAI implementation should be a priority for companies developing software in the B2B sector, to maximize the benefits of this technology while minimizing risks for all stakeholders.

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